

Econometric Analysis of the Determinants of Entertainment and Media Growth in Nigeria ARDL Approach

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ABSTRACT

The growth enhancing potentials of entertainment and media industry in Nigeria as a diversification strategy has attracted attention in the recent past. Following the rebasing of Nigeria's GDP in 2014, the entertainment subsector was shown to be amongst the robust components of the GDP. Given the importance of this sector to Nigerian economy, this study set out to investigate the determinants of entertainment and media growth in Nigeria. Time series data covering from 1981 to 2021 on the Entertainment output (ENT), Real GDP, government expenditure on education (EDU), per capita income (PCI), internet (INT) and cellular subscriptions (CEL) were utilized to estimate an ARDL cointegration model. The result showed that government expenditure on education (EDU), real GDP, internet (INT) and cellular subscriptions (CEL) are positively related to entertainment growth both in the long-run and short-run while per capita income (PCI) is negatively related to entertainment growth in Nigeria. The result indicates that the variables in the estimated ARDL model are cointegrated and share long-run relationship. The speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium after a shock is 41 percent annually. We recommend that government should create attractive investment climate in the entertainment industry to incentivize investors and create entertainment and media institutes to harness millions of talented people. There should be a strong regulatory framework for copyright protection and prevention of piracy. Policies that will drive economic growth will have multiplier effect on household income and access to both internet and cellular subscriptions which enhances entertainment and media consumption.

Keywords: Entertainment, ARDL, Bounds test.

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, the entertainment and media industry have witnessed tremendous growth especially with widespread expansion of digital infrastructure. Entertainment and media (E&M) activities are ranked among the sectors with very high potential to create wealth and employment opportunities to greater proportion of the population. The industry comprises of advertising; video (film making), television and radio broadcasting; music and games. These also include sports, live shows, comedy and skit-making, streaming in social media and reality shows. This sector employs numerous professionals ranging from actors, musicians, marketers and distributors which contributes to overall workforce driving economic activities. More so, the value chain of entertainment and media encompasses ancillary businesses such as vendors, caterers, events planners, hospitality and tourist activities which creates multiplier effect on economic growth. With the widespread access to mobile cellular and internet connectivity, entertainment and media have become a very profitable industry and huge investment opportunity given that digital and virtual contents are accessed with ease. This has led to projection that virtual entertainment will generate more revenue than physical entertainment in the coming years (PricewaterhouseCoopers, PwC, 2020)

Despite the rate of growth of E&M, research on the interlinkages with the economy has been very scanty. This may not be unconnected with paucity of organized data in this area. Apart from the United States of America which may be regarded as world entertainment hub because of the level of development of their E&M industries where various data sets are documented, many other national entertainment and media sectors are still evolving. Most data sets are accessed from divergent sources. However, the PwC consulting group has been providing data of E&M through publication of their Global Entertainment and Media Outlook for various years. This contains mainly breakdown of revenue and forecast from each segment of E&M. According to PwC (2021), the global entertainment revenue had declined in 2020 to \$2trillion from \$2.1trillion in 2019. This was attributed to the Covid-19 pandemic associated containment strategies which limited entertainment activities. However, lockdowns and physical restriction on E&M venues triggered growth in digital entertainment consumption as subscription to virtual entertainment platforms soared. In 2020, there were 4.6 billion smartphone connections and about 1.1 billion household fixed broadband around the globe. As access to internet and data became a lifeline, it attracted 34.1 percent in 2020 in global entertainment spending (PwC,2021).

Nigerian entertainment industry has been rated amongst the fastest growing creative industries in the world and has the potential to significantly drive economic growth. The industry employs about 1.2 million people contributing about 2.3 percent to Nigeria's GDP as at 2021 (NBS,2021). Modern entertainment in Nigeria revolves mainly around home movies with the creation of Nollywood in 1992 and the expansion in the musical entertainment segment. The Nollywood industry produces about 2500 movies annually (ITA,2023) which indicate the widespread acceptance of home movie as a form of entertainment in the country. More recently, there has been combination of subscription-based entertainment, digital media entertainment powered by quantum growth in mobile cellular and internet penetration as well as physical/live shows both in music, comedy and reality shows. Expectedly, Nigeria has up to 70 percent of youth population (WDI,2022) who consume these entertainment products on various multimedia devices and electronic gadgets. Due to income generating opportunities associated with digital content creation and streaming, many young people engage themselves in both video and audio forms of entertainment production. Thus, it is apposite to state that entertainment growth in Nigeria is driven by demography and telecommunication technology.

Following the activities in the entertainment industry, PwC in their country-specific entertainment and media outlook analyzed each entertainment segment activities and their contribution to the Nigerian economy. It was projected that Nigeria's entertainment industry is capable of becoming the country's greatest export with annual growth rate of 8.6 percent and a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 19.3 percent between 2018 and 2023. In 2021, 2.3 percent of Nigeria's GDP came from film industry contributing about N239 billion (\$660 million). It was further predicted that film industry's export earnings may hit \$1 billion in the next five years (PwC,2022). The estimated revenue of N292 billion (\$806 million) from motion picture and music recording industry was surpassed as it contributed N730 billion (\$2 billion) to GDP in 2020 despite the economic slowdown occasioned by the covid-19 pandemic. Similarly, the traditional TV and home video industry generated N251 billion (\$692 million) in 2021 and it is predicted to generate N313 billion (\$865 million) by 2025 (PwC,2022).

Following the rebasing of Nigerian economy in 2014, it was established that the entertainment and telecommunication sectors contributed significantly to the making of the GDP but were not adequately captured in the final GDP figures. Economic diversification into this growing industry has the capacity to generate higher revenue to the government, create more employment and harness the numerous talents amongst the youthful population in Nigeria. These will further

enhance the growth of the economy. However, there is generally very sparse empirical studies on entertainment and growth while studies on the determinants of growth in the entertainment industry is non-existent. Such studies are needed as their findings will serve as a guide to policy-makers. To the best of the researchers' knowledge, this is the first attempt at such research. The objective of this study therefore, is to econometrically analyze the determinants of entertainment and media growth in the Nigerian economy. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: following section one introduction, section two, present literature review, section three handles the methodology of the study while section 4 presents results and its analysis. Section five is devoted to policy implication and conclusion the paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Labour economics classifies human activities into two broad categories – work and leisure. Both work and leisure are measured in time spent in each activity. Leisure is regarded as activities people engage in during their free time or time free from any sense of obligation or compulsion. Thus leisure is broadly characterized as time not spent at work. The concept of leisure is further broken down to recreation and entertainment. Recreation literally means re-creation of the body and soul after work. It includes both physical and mental rejuvenation (Hennig-Thurau and Mark, 2019). The concept of entertainment is subsumed into recreational activities. Basically, entertainment is seen as anything that can stimulate, encourage or generate a pleasurable condition capable of diverting one's attention. According to Vogel (2011), entertainment involves the act which diverts, amuses or causes someone's time to pass agreeably. It is usually interesting and very appealing which can move the consumers emotionally. Entertainment is usually very attractive that consumers have expectations towards enjoying its contents. Thus it can be defined in its cause-and-effect connection. The content is the cause while the satisfied mind or psychological state is the effect which can be achieved through either passive or active participation. Empirical studies on entertainment and economy nexus is very scanty. This is unconnected to the lack of data on specific drivers of entertainment particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. Attempt was made to review available empirical studies in this area. Martins and Abdelrasaq (2014) explored the relationship between ICT-driven entertainment industry and economic growth in Nigeria using quarterly data from 2010q1 to 2013q4. The variables included in the study are – GDP, ICT as share of GDP, Inflation rate, Public trust and Entertainment as share of GDP. They estimated their models with OLS and FMOLS and found that ICT enhances productivity is the entertainment industry. Mannan et al (2016) investigated the impact of entertainment industry on the economy. They utilized annual data on GDP, firm production and number of matches played for 7 countries. They estimated a pool mean group (PMG) model and found that there is evidence of positive and significant long-run relationship between entertainment and economic growth. On his part, Shivganga (2020) carried out an empirical study of entertainment industry and its impact on Indian economy through a survey research. He concluded that entertainment industry expansion yields economic growth in India. Bowen (2023) studied the influence of cultural and creative industry development on economic growth of the tertiary industry in Shanghai and Jiangsu Province while utilizing data from 2010 to 2020 on GDP and emerging cultural and creative industry. They estimated a fixed effect model and concluded that economic development is positively influenced by a boom in these emerging industries.

2.1 Entertainment and Media Industry in Nigeria

Nigeria's E&M is one of the fastest growing creative industries in the world and its Nollywood industry took the second position in the creation of films and movies in the world, first being Hollywood (ITA, 2023). According to PwC (2019), the E&M in Nigeria comprises of music, internet, books, radio, cinema, TV, data consumption, newspapers/magazines, video-games, virtual reality and E-sports segments. PwC consulting compiles and publishes data and forecasts on these segments. Nigerian E&M markets were analyzed between 2014 and 2018 while forecasting from 2019 to 2023. Based on available data, the revenue from the E&M market in Nigeria was about \$4500 million as at 2018 and projected to increase to \$10,801 billion by 2023. The CAGR (cumulative average growth rate) is projected to be 19.3 percent. This is more than 5 times the anticipated average growth rate of the real GDP of about 3.2 percent within the same period. Figure 1 below shows E&M revenue from 2014 to 2018 (blue bar) and the forecast revenue from 2019 to 2023 (red bar). This shows a steady increase in E&M revenue.

Among the individual segments, revenue from the internet segment dominated total E&M revenue. This is followed by the television and home video segment. Table 1 shows that in 2018, the total E&M revenue was \$4467 million while internet revenue stood at \$3272 million in the same year showing about 73.2 percent contribution to total E&M revenue. This reveals that there is growth in mobile telephony coverage and wider penetration of internet connectivity with attendant increase in expenditure on data and consumption of online entertainment products. As at 2018, there is about 72 million active smartphone connections with 1.3 million high-speed and 65 million low-speed connections (PwC, 2019). Based on the forecast, internet E&M revenue is expected to increase to \$9349 million by 2023 which represents about 86.6 percent of Total E&M revenue forecast. In 2019, the television segment stood at \$771 million and contributed about 14 percent to the total E&M revenue of \$5553 million. TV and video segment forecast for 2023 was \$904 million which represents about 8.4 percent of total E&M revenue forecast of \$10,801. The growth in TV and video segment is traceable to subscription revenue. This is because subscription-based entertainment is very popular in Nigeria. Even though Multichoice dominates the subscription market due to live-streaming of sports, other players like Startimes, iRoko TV, Netflix, Amazon Prime video are equally contributing to the growth of the revenue. According to ITA (2023), Nigeria ranked higher than South Africa in Pay-TV with about 7.4 million households' subscriptions in 2023. It is further projected that Nigeria's household Pay-TV subscribers will reach 10 million in 2025 representing about 21.2 percent of the market in Africa.

Table 1: Nigeria Entertainment and Media Market by Segment 2014 – 2023 (US\$ million)

Segment	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	CAGR 2018-2023
Books	\$23	\$24	\$25	\$27	\$28	\$29	\$30	\$31	\$33	\$34	3.9%
Business to-Business	\$11	\$12	\$13	\$14	\$15	\$16	\$17	\$18	\$19	\$19	5.7%
Cinema	\$7	\$7	\$10	\$11	\$12	\$14	\$15	\$16	\$17	\$18	7.9%
Internet	\$1073	\$1306	\$1656	\$2403	\$3272	\$4300	\$5434	\$6686	\$8045	\$9349	23.4%
Magazine	\$100	\$102	\$105	\$107	\$109	\$111	\$113	\$115	\$117	\$119	1.7%
Music	\$26	\$27	\$30	\$32	\$34	\$36	\$38	\$40	\$42	\$44	5.2%
Newspapers	\$91	\$90	\$90	\$90	\$90	\$91	\$91	\$90	\$90	\$89	-0.3%
Out-of-home	\$93	\$99	\$104	\$112	\$118	\$125	\$131	\$137	\$142	\$147	4.5%
Radio	\$42	\$44	\$38	\$40	\$42	\$44	\$47	\$49	\$51	\$54	5.1%
TV and Video	\$538	\$568	\$619	\$681	\$732	\$771	\$806	\$838	\$871	\$904	4.3%
Video games	\$19	\$22	\$39	\$51	\$67	\$85	\$104	\$126	\$150	\$176	21.4%
Total E&M revenue	\$2005	\$2283	\$2700	\$3528	\$4467	\$5553	\$6739	\$8041	\$9448	\$10801	19.3%

Source: PwC (2019)

The music segment of the entertainment industry generates more revenue from export and streaming. It employs over a million people including stakeholders like producers, artists, promoters, distributors, managers and marketers (ITA,2023). As talents are being discovered, many new studios and music productions are created which helps in sustaining the industry. Nigeria has many internationally rated Grammy award winning artists like Davido, BurnerBoy, Wizkid and many more. It generated over \$8 billion to the Nigeria economy 2021 with potential to attract more investment. Due to the lockdown of public and physical concerts occasioned by the covid-19 pandemic, Nigeria recorded an increase in internet music subscribers to the tune of 154.3 million as at December 2020 which provided more opportunities for more revenue from digital song sales and online streaming. The revenue of the music streaming market is projected to hit over \$113 million by the end of 2022 with an expected annual growth rate of 12.56% between 2022 and 2026 (ITA,2023).

The achievements in Nigeria’s entertainment industry has been plagued with many challenges. Unlike other developed industries of the West, Nigeria’s entertainment industry is poorly regulated and largely unstructured. This makes for production of low standard films and music. Treichel (2010) posits that the marketing and distribution links of Nigeria’s entertainment products are ad hoc with very limited access to finance. He further advocates for establishment of strong global links which will improve quality at every stage of the value chain. Amongst the many challenges, issues of copyright piracy and counterfeiting are the most pronounced. There are copious evidence of violations of piracy and intellectual property rights. With the exception of digital contents, many of the CDs and hardcopies of production in the Nigerian market are pirated. Even though there are significant efforts to strengthen intellectual property rights in Nigeria (ITA,2023). One of such efforts is the recent passage of a bill that criminalizes

the broadcast of any digital production without obtaining permission from the creator. Violation of this law attracts a fine ranging from N100,000 to N2 million naira or up to a year of imprisonment. Similarly, the regulator of the entertainment industry in Nigeria - National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) – provided the amended 6th edition of the broadcasting code which outlaws exclusivity. The code is meant to regulate content exclusivity and enforce content sharing. It equally empowers NBC to determine prices that content can be sold to sub-licensees by copyright holders. Even though it has been argued that this sub-licensing of content and regulation of pricing may reduce the attractiveness of the industry for large participants that thrive on exclusive content (ITA,2023). Other challenges of Nigeria’s entertainment industry include: epileptic electricity supply to power production and concert venues; poor road network which usually impede access to movie locations; high cost of procuring standard entertainment equipment; lack of standard concert venues; insecurity; inexperienced managers and promoters; lack of foreign exchange; patronage of foreign entertainment and subscription-based products by Nigerian consumers.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data

We utilized time series data on six variables for this study. Table 2 shows the summarized the variables. Data set for Entertainment, Real Gross Domestic Product and Government Expenditure on Education were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Annual Statistical Bulletin (2022) while the data set for share of individuals using internet per 100 people and mobile-cellular-subscriptions-per-100-people were sourced from Our-World-in-Data (OWID, 2022). The Per capita income was sourced from the World Development Indicator(WDI,2022). The range of the data covers 1981 to 2021 except Internet access and cellular phone access that covered between 1996 and 2021. The inclusion of internet and mobile cellular subscription data set follows the interlinkages between media and entertainment. Most digital entertainment contents are mostly accessed through the internet compliant devices. Empirically, entertainment consumption depends on national productivity measured by the Real GDP and Per capita income as demand for entertainment is a function of disposal income. We used government expenditure on education to proxy literate population of young people who are mostly fun seekers and demand more of digital entertainment. All the variables in this study have been transformed in natural logarithm in order to smoothen the data and reduce incidence of outliers.

Table 2: Description of Variables

Variables	Representation	Source	Units
Entertainment (ENT)	Entertainment, Art and Recreation Output	CBN Statistical Bulletin 2022	Billions/Naira
Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP)	Gross Domestic Product at 2010 constant prices	CBN Statistical Bulletin 2022	Billions/Naira
Education (EDU)	Government Expenditure on Education	CBN Statistical Bulletin 2022	Billions/Naira
Per Capita Income (PCI)	Per Capita National Income	WDI 2022	Thousands/Dollars
Internet (INT)	Share of individuals using internet per 100 people	OWID 2022	Millions
Cellular (CEL)	Mobile-cellular-subscriptions-per-100-people	OWID 2022	Millions

3.2 Model Specification

In this study, we hypothesize that Entertainment is a function of Real GDP, Education expenditure, Per capita income, internet access and mobile cellular subscription. Thus, the functional relationship of the model is given as

$$ENT = f(RGDP, EDU, PCI, INT, CEL) \tag{1}$$

Where the variables are as described in Table 2

We then specified the initial econometric model as follow

$$ENT = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RGDP_t + \beta_2 EDU_t + \beta_3 PCI_t + \beta_4 INT_t + \beta_5 CEL_t + u_t \tag{2}$$

There is preponderance of time series model which can be estimated to ascertain the existence of long-run and short-run dynamics between selected variables. The choice of model mainly depends on the order of integration of the time series variables. In this study, we model the equilibrium relationships between the variables according to the bounds testing approach to cointegration based on the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) framework (Pesaran et al.,2001). The advantage of ARDL model are that: (1) it can be implemented in a fractionally integrated variable(s). That is, variables that are integrated of order zero can be modelled together with variables integrated of order one without necessarily obtaining spurious result (2) unlike most time series models, ARDL model can be estimated in a single-equation set-up, (3) different variables in the model can be assigned different lag-lengths (4) it is possible to implement this model for short time series and (5) it simple to implement and interpret.

Following the ARDL model (p,q) of equation (2), we formulate a generic unrestricted error correction model (UECM) as follows:

$$\Delta y_t = \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \beta_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^{q-1} \alpha_j \Delta x_{t-j} + \phi [y_{t-1} - \{\beta + \delta_i x_{t-i}\}] + \varepsilon_t \tag{3}$$

Where Δy_t is difference stationary growth rate of the real ENT, Δx_t is a vector of difference stationary explanatory variables (RGDP,EDU, PCI,INT,CEL), β and α are short-run coefficients of the determinants of entertainment in our model, δ_i represents long-run coefficients of the lags of the explanatory variables, ϕ represent the speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium relationship while ε_t is a white noise error term. A generic model akin to equation (2) which is represented by the term in the bracket is the long-run equilibrium relationship which can be written as follows:

$$y = \beta + \delta_i \cdot x + u_t \tag{4}$$

From equation (4), u_t is distributed as an I(0) process before cointegration can be concluded. Bounds testing approach to cointegration as proposed by Pesaran et al (2001) is based on the F- statistics or Wald test which is non-standard under the asymptotic distribution. The test is constructed under the null hypothesis of no cointegration between the examined variables, irrespective of whether they are distributed as purely I(0) or I(1). To implement the bounds test, the null hypothesis is tested on equation (3) based on the joint significance test performed as follows:

$$H_0 : \delta_i = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad H_0 : \delta_i \neq 0$$

Pesaran et al (2001) constructed two sets of critical values for significance test at a given level. One set assumes that all the variables are integrated of order zero while the second assumes that they are all integrated of order one. If the calculated F-statistics exceeds the upper critical bounds value, the null hypothesis of no cointegration is rejected. If the calculated F-statistics lies below the lower critical bounds value, the null hypothesis of no cointegration is not rejected and if the calculated F-statistics fall between the lower and upper critical bounds value, the test is inconclusive. After the identification of a long-run relationship, the short-run and long-run dynamic model for equation (3) can be estimated from the following ARDL specification

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta ENT_t = & \tilde{a}_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \tilde{a}_1 \Delta RGDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^k \tilde{a}_2 \Delta EDU_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^k \tilde{a}_3 \Delta PCI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^k \tilde{a}_4 \Delta INT_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=0}^k \tilde{a}_5 \Delta CEL_{t-i} + ec_{t-1} + \varphi_t \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Where ec_{t-1} is the first lag of the stationary residual from long-run equation (4). Further tests are performed to check the stability of the estimated parameters on the model.

4. RESULT PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

In other proceed with the implementation of ARDL model, we carried out unit root test using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (1979) (ADF) test to confirm that none of the series are distributed as I(2) stochastic process. The test is based on a null hypothesis of non-stationarity in the series. The result of the test at level and first difference of the series are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: ADF Unit Root Test

Variables	Test statistic	P - v a l u e value	Remark
ENT	-1.0922	0.9900	Nonstationary
RGDP	-0.9199	0.7710	Nonstationary
EDU	-2.3574	0.1606	Nonstationary
PCI	-2.5847	0.1045	Nonstationary
INT	-4.2911	0.0027	Stationary
CEL	-2.7908	0.0751	Stationary
Δ ENT	-4.3430	0.0014	Stationary
Δ RGDP	-3.9874	0.0037	Stationary
Δ EDU	-7.9740	0.0000	Stationary
Δ PCI	-5.7171	0.0000	Stationary

The result of the ADF unit root tests indicate INT and CEL are integrated of order zero while others are integrated of order one. This confirms that none of the variables is integrated of order two which indicate that bounds test can be implemented. We estimated a restricted error correction model with constant from equation (3). We selected the maximum lag length of the parsimonious model based on Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). The appropriate lag order for this study is ARDL (1,0,1,1,1,1) from which we obtained the result of the Bounds test as presented in Table 4.

Table 4: ARDL Bounds Test for Cointegration

F-Statistics	(ENT/RGDP, EDU, PCI, INT, CEL)				24.56*`***`****	
Critical Bounds Values						
10%		5%		1%		
I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	
2.334	3.515	2.794	4.148	3.976	5.691	
1.990	2.940	2.270	3.280	2.880	3.990	

Note: k = 5, * =1%, ** = 5%, * = 10%**

Given that the computed F-statistics of 24.56 is greater than the upper critical bounds at all conventional levels of significance of 3.515, 4.148 and 5.691 respectively, we conclude that the variables in our model are cointegrated. Therefore, a long-run equilibrium relationship exists

among the selected variables in our model. Given the existence of a long-run relationship, we estimate the long-run model of equation (4) from where we extracted the restricted error correction term of equation (5). Table 5 presents the result of the long run model.

Table 5: Long Run Model Result
Dependent Variable: ENT

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.*
ENT(-1)	0.593	7.559	0.0000*
PCI	-0.103	-0.460	0.6531
EDU	0.033	1.228	0.2428
EDU(-1)	-0.088	-3.249	0.0070*
RGDP	0.977	3.773	0.0027*
RGDP(-1)	-0.547	-1.476	0.1657
INT	0.003	0.0815	0.9363
INT(-1)	0.103	2.900	0.0133*
CEL	0.013	0.781	0.4498
CEL(-1)	-0.073	-3.138	0.0086*
C	-1.745	-0.601	0.5592

*=5% significance level

Based on the selected ARDL (1,0,1,1,1,1) model, the estimated coefficient of the first lag of Entertainment [ENT(-1)] is positively signed and statistically significant. This may imply that previous period's entertainment investment and expenditure is positively related to entertainment growth in the longrun. The estimated coefficient of the per capita income (PCI) is negatively signed and statistically insignificant. This is an indication that entertainment consumption may not be a priority to people in the longrun. Even though the estimated coefficient of Education (EDU) is positively related to entertainment growth in the longrun, it statistically insignificant. However, its first lag is negatively related to entertainment growth in the longrun. The estimated coefficient of real GDP (RGDP) is statistically significant and positively related to entertainment growth in the longrun. This means that as the economy grows, entertainment consumption will also grow.

The estimated coefficient of the internet (INT) and cellular subscriptions (CEL) are positively signed which indicate that access to internet and mobile cellular subscription is favourable to entertainment consumption in the longrun. The short-run dynamic equilibrium relationship based on ARDL (1,0,1,1,1,1) model which indicate the error correction model (ECM) is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Short-run Error Correction Model Result
Dependent Variable: ENT

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob*.
D(EDU)	0.0333	2.3519	0.0296*
D(RGDP)	0.9776	8.3721	0.0000*
D(INT)	0.0038	0.2116	0.8347
D(CEL)	0.0139	1.4293	0.1691
COINTEQ*	-0.4069	-17.638	0.0000*

*=5% significance level

In the shortrun model, all the estimated coefficients of the model are positively related to entertainment growth. The estimated coefficients of EDU (0.0333) indicate that a one percent increase in government expenditure on education will on the average lead to about 3 percent growth in entertainment consumption. The estimated coefficients of RGDP (0.9776) indicate that a one percent increase in real GDP will on the average lead to about 97 percent growth in entertainment consumption. This result further indicate that a growing economy will demand for more leisure and entertainment. Similarly, the estimated coefficients of INT (0.0038) and CEL (0.0139) indicate that a one percent increase in internet subscription will on the average lead to about 0.3 percent growth in entertainment consumption while a one percent increase in cellular subscription will on the average lead to about one percent growth in entertainment consumption. This result further indicate that modern entertainment depends on digital media driving by growth in internet connectivity. The result of the error correction model indicate that the estimated error correction term COINTEQ is negatively signed and statistically significant at all conventional levels with a coefficient of -0.4069. This coefficient shows the speed of adjustment to longrun equilibrium after a shock. The speed of adjustment of shortrun deviations from the longrun equilibrium path is about 41 percent showing that there is 41 percent adjustment of previous year’s deviation from longrun equilibrium as a result of shock back to long-run equilibrium in the current year.

4.1 Stability Test

We performed selected post estimation diagnostic tests to ascertain the stability of the estimated model. We performed the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ stability tests, Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test and Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test. The result of the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity test is reported in Table 7 while the serial correlation is reported in Table 8 . Figures x and X reports the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ stability tests result.

Table 7: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test

F-statistic	0.842661	Prob. F(12,12)	0.6142
Obs*R-squared	11.43266	Prob. Chi-Square(12)	0.4922

The null hypothesis of Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity is that the residual from the estimated model is homoscedastic. Based on the result, the probability value of the F-statistic (0.6142) is greater than 5 percent level of significance which indicate we cannot reject the null hypothesis of constant variance in the estimated residual. The null hypothesis of Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation is that the residual from the estimated model is no autocorrelated. Based on the result, the probability value of the F-statistic (0.0823) is greater than 5 percent level of significance. Thus we cannot reject the null hypothesis of no serial

correlation in the residual.

Figure 2 and 3 indicate that, at 5 percent level of significance, the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ test statistics lies within the critical bounds. This confirms that the coefficients of the estimated model is stable within the period selected for this study.

Table 8: Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation

F-statistic	3.239823	Prob. F(2,10)	0.0823
Obs*R-squared	9.829771	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0073

Figure 2: Plot of CUSUM.

Figure 3: Plot of CUSUM of Squares.

5. POLICY IMPLICATION OF FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

Given the findings of the study, there are far-reaching policy implications which can stimulate the growth of the entertainment and media industry in Nigeria. Economic diversification has been a topical issue in Nigeria since independence. This constant calls for diversification stems from government over-dependence on oil as a major source of revenue. The findings of this study highlighted the potential of entertainment and media industry as a veritable diversification strategy. Given the huge market and demand of entertainment, government should create targeted

policies and incentives to encourage investments and entrepreneurship in this sector. This will in turn stimulate economic growth, job creation and bring in more revenue to the government. Our estimated model showed a positive relationship between education expenditure and entertainment growth. This implies that an educated population will have higher tendency to demand for entertainment products. More so, majority of fun seekers fall within the school age where entertainment market is more robust. Thus, there is need for policy makers to prioritize investment in education. The finding of a positive correlation between internet and cellular subscriptions with entertainment and media support the idea that entertainment is driving by a strong digital infrastructure. This implies that investment in digital infrastructure should be encouraged. Policy-makers should therefore implement policies that will promote greater access and penetration of high speed internet and affordable cellular services. This will in turn foster the growth of the entertainment industry and enable content creation, distribution and consumption. The study focused on investigating the determinants of entertainment and media growth in Nigeria. The entertainment industry is a booming industry around the world with high percentage contribution to economic growth in many countries. Nigeria is amongst the economies with the fastest growing entertainment and industries. The motivation for this study stemmed from the recent discovery of the growth enhancing potentials of the entertainment and telecommunication industries prior to the rebasing of Nigeria's GDP. Thus, an econometric analysis of the determinants of entertainment and media growth in Nigeria is apposite. We utilized time series data on selected variables in an ARDL modelling framework. The result showed that government expenditure on education (EDU), real GDP, internet (INT) and cellular subscriptions (CEL) are positively related to entertainment growth both in the long-run and short-run. However, the result indicated a negative relationship between per capita income and entertainment growth in Nigeria. The result further indicated that the speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium after a shock is 41 percent. Based on our findings, we recommend that government should create attractive investment climate in the entertainment industry to incentivize investors. We equally recommend the creation and strengthening of entertainment and media institutes to harness millions of talented entertainment enthusiasts and therefrom create jobs and empowerment opportunities to teeming youth population in Nigeria. There should be a strong regulatory framework for copyright protection and prevention of piracy. Finally, there is need to implement policies that drives economic growth which will in turn lead to improvement in household income and access to both internet and cellular subscriptions which enhances entertainment and media consumption.

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